

ROLE OF OXIDATIVE STRESS IN MIGRAINE

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Abstract

Objective: Oxidative stress, resulting from an imbalance between reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and antioxidant defenses, plays a significant role in migraine pathogenesis. This study contributes to ongoing research by focusing on oxidative stress as a potential cause of migraine, specifically through the comparison of biochemical markers superoxide dismutase (SOD) and malondialdehyde (MDA).

Study Design: This was a case control study.

Place and Duration of Study: This study was conducted at the Neuro OPD of PNS Shifa Hospital; Karachi. The ethical approval was taken from Bahria University Health Sciences Karachi (BUHSCK). The duration of the study was 6 months it started in February 2024- July 2024.

Methodology: Migraine patients between age 20-40 years were included in cases and healthy participants were included in controls. The calculated sample size of 246 subjects were divided into two groups, out which 123 were cases and 123 were controls. Venous blood sample was taken for measuring SOD & MDA. The obtained results were statistically analyzed by SPSS version 23. P-values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results: Baseline characteristics showed no significant differences between controls and migraine patients in age, BMI, SBP, and DBP ($p > 0.05$), except for temperature, which was significantly lower in migraine patients ($p = 0.027$). Median levels of superoxide dismutase (SOD) and malondialdehyde (MDA) were 41 nm/mL (IQR = 29) and 2 U/mL (IQR = 1) in controls, and 10 nm/mL (IQR = 4) and 4 U/mL (IQR = 1) in migraine patients, respectively. The Mann-Whitney U test revealed a significant difference in both SOD and MDA levels between the groups ($p < 0.01$), indicating increased oxidative stress in migraine patients.

Conclusion: Our study concludes that migraine patients exhibit reduced superoxide dismutase (SOD) levels and elevated malondialdehyde (MDA), highlighting the involvement of oxidative stress in migraine pathogenesis. These findings may help healthcare professionals develop more targeted management strategies addressing underlying oxidative stress

INTRODUCTION

Migraine is one of the most prevalent neurological disorders encountered in primary care. According to the Global Burden of Disease survey, migraine ranks as the second leading cause of disability worldwide and the foremost among young women, largely due to hormonal influences (1). Approximately 2% of the global population is affected by migraine, which significantly impacts patients, their families, and society (2). It is a complex, episodic sensory disorder characterized primarily by recurrent headaches, often accompanied by nausea, photophobia, and phonophobia. Migraines are broadly classified based on the presence or absence of aura. Migraine with aura, typically of visual nature, precedes the headache and may last at least five minutes (3). Visual auras can present as scintillating scotomas or expanding blind spots. Other manifestations include reversible aphasia, sensory disturbances (e.g., tingling), motor symptoms, brainstem dysfunction (e.g., unsteadiness), and cranial nerve-related issues, typically lasting 5 to 60 minutes (4).

Oxidative stress results from an imbalance between reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and antioxidant defense mechanisms. This imbalance contributes to the pathogenesis of various diseases, including diabetes, cancer, cardiovascular conditions, and neurological disorders (5). Elevated ROS and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) can disrupt intracellular signaling, damage proteins and DNA, and impair cellular organelles. Multiple mechanisms contribute to oxidative stress in migraine, including altered mitochondrial energy metabolism, nitric oxide (NO) release, inflammatory mediators, and increased polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) in cell membranes, which enhance lipid peroxidation risk (6). Antioxidant defenses comprise non-enzymatic molecules like glutathione and vitamins A, C, and E, as well as enzymatic agents such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) (6). Research shows that migraine patients exhibit elevated serum levels of malondialdehyde (MDA), a marker of lipid peroxidation, and NO metabolites, along with reduced total antioxidant capacity and lower enzymatic antioxidant activity, indicating

oxidative and nitrosative stress involvement in migraine pathophysiology. The frequency of migraine attacks is also correlated with increased oxidative stress markers and decreased antioxidant levels (7). Common migraine triggers—such as fasting, stress, hormonal changes, weather fluctuations, alcohol, strong odors, bright light, and loud sounds—are thought to induce oxidative stress via mitochondrial dysfunction (8). Oxidative stress activates transient receptor potential (TRP) channels located on trigeminal nerve endings in the meninges, potentially contributing to migraine pain (9).

Given the growing evidence linking oxidative stress to migraine pathophysiology, assessing oxidative biomarkers offers critical insights. Understanding the redox imbalance in migraine patients can contribute to the identification of novel therapeutic targets and management strategies. The objective of this study is to evaluate the role of oxidative stress in migraine by comparing levels of superoxide dismutase (SOD) and malondialdehyde (MDA) between migraine patients and healthy controls.

METHODOLOGY

This was a case-control study conducted in the Neurology Outpatient Department (OPD) of PNS Shifa Hospital, Karachi, over a duration of six months, from February 2024 to July 2024. Participants who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled. The inclusion criteria comprised both genders aged 20–40 years, patients with a history of migraine presenting to the Neurology OPD of PNS Shifa Hospital, and age-matched healthy controls. Exclusion criteria included participants with any other type of headache, inflammatory diseases, those taking vitamin D or zinc supplements, and individuals on antioxidants or immunity-boosting medications.

A total sample size of 246 participants was calculated using OpenEpi Version 3, with a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error. Group A consisted of 123 migraine cases, while Group B included 123 age-matched healthy controls. The sample size was determined considering the prevalence of migraine in Pakistan, as reported by Herekar et al. in 2017, using convenient sampling.

Data collection involved a questionnaire divided into two sections. Appendix I covered demographic and general characteristics of the participants, while Appendix II included the ID-Migraine scale for migraine identification and the Headache Impact Test-6 (HIT-6) scale to assess the impact of headache. Ethical approval was obtained, and informed consent was taken from patients.

Measurement of Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) Activity

The activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD) was determined based on its ability to inhibit the oxidation of adrenaline to adrenochrome in an alkaline pH. To begin, **0.15 mL of ice-chilled chloroform** and **0.75 mL of ethanol** were added to **0.1 mL of serum** and thoroughly mixed. The mixture was centrifuged at **3000 rpm for 15 minutes**, and the supernatant was carefully separated. To the supernatant, **1.0 mL of 0.1M carbonate-bicarbonate buffer (pH 10.2)**, **0.5 mL of 0.6 mM EDTA**, and **1.8 mM epinephrine**

were added. The reaction mixture's absorbance was measured at **480 nm**, which reflects the enzymatic activity of SOD through its inhibitory effects on adrenochrome formation. (10)

Measurement of Malondialdehyde (MDA) Levels

Malondialdehyde (MDA), a key biomarker of lipid peroxidation, was quantified by its reaction with thiobarbituric acid (TBA) under acidic conditions to form a pink-colored chromogen. For this assay, **0.1 mL of serum** was mixed with **3.0 mL of glacial acetic acid** and **3.0 mL of 1% TBA** prepared in **2% NaOH**. The mixture was then heated in a boiling water bath for **15 minutes** to facilitate the reaction. After boiling, the solution was allowed to cool to room temperature. The absorbance of the resultant chromogen was recorded at **532 nm**, providing a quantitative measure of MDA concentration, which correlates with the extent of lipid peroxidation (11).

RESULTS:

Table 1: Mean Comparison of Baseline Characteristics between Migraine and Controls

Parameters	Control (n=123)		Migraine (n=123)		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Age (years)	33.6	4.7	33.2	4.6	0.54
Weight (kg)	68.0	10.0	69.4	9.2	0.23
Height (m)	1.6	0.1	1.6	0.1	0.65
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.7	5.1	28.4	4.8	0.21
SBP	122.2	9.0	121.5	10.0	0.57
DBP	81.8	4.4	81.9	4.7	0.87

Table 2: Association of Cast, Gender and House Environment with Migraine

Characteristics		Group				p-value
		Control (n=123)		Migraine (n=123)		
		n	%	n	%	
Cast	Balochi	23	18.7	21	17.1	0.75
	Muhajir	3	2.4	7	5.7	
	Pathan	24	19.5	23	18.7	
	Punjabi	46	37.4	40	32.5	
	Sindhi	14	11.4	18	14.6	
	Siraiki	13	10.6	14	11.4	

Gender	Male	24	19.5	18	14.6	0.30
	Female	99	80.5	105	85.4	
House environment	House	16	13.0	10	8.1	0.31
	Bungalow	7	5.7	11	8.9	
	Apartment	100	81.3	102	82.9	

*p<0.05 was considered statistically significant using Pearson Chi Square test

Table 3: Association of Milk, Fish and Fuzzy Drink with Migraine

Variables		Group				p-value
		Control (n=123)		Migraine (n=123)		
		n	%	n	%	
Milk in take	Yes	83	67.5	80	65.0	0.10
	Occasionally	6	4.9	1	0.8	
	No	34	27.6	42	34.1	
Fish intake	Yes	65	52.8	77	62.6	0.29
	Occasionally	12	9.8	9	7.3	
	No	46	37.4	37	30.1	
Fuzzy drink intake	Yes	52	42.3	41	33.3	0.33
	Occasionally	33	26.8	40	32.5	
	No	38	30.9	42	34.1	

*p<0.05 was considered statistically significant using Pearson Chi Square test

Table 4: Observed Characteristics of Migraine Patients (N=123)

Characteristics		n	%
Migraine triggers	Caffeine/ screen	1	0.8
	Less sleep	3	2.4
	Less sleep/screen	21	17.1
	Physical activity	1	0.8
	Physical activity/ less sleep	43	35
	Physical activity/screen/ Less sleep	22	17.9
	Screen	1	0.8
	None	31	25.2
Family history of migraine	No	123	100.0
Caffeine intake	Yes	50	40.7
Physical activity	Yes	92	74.8
Co morbidity	Yes	20	16.3
Self-medication	Yes	71	57.7
Medicines used	Inderal/ topiramate	123	100.0
Fluid consumption	Adequate	123	100.0
Intensity of migraine	Moderate	26	21.1

	Severe	97	78.9
Symptoms of headache	Nausea	39	31.7
	Nausea/photophobia/ phonophobia	48	29
	Nausea/vomiting	1	0.8
	Nausea/vomiting/photophobia/phonophobia	1	0.8
	Phonophobia	1	0.8
	Photophobia	30	24.6
	Photophobia/phonophobia	1	0.8
	None	3	2.4
Characteristics of headache	Unilateral	57	46.3
	Unilateral/pulsating	23	18.7
	Unilateral/pulsating/throbbing	3	2.4
	Unilateral/throbbing	20	16.3
	Unilateral/throbbing/pulsating	20	16.3
Sleep Hours per night		7.6	±1.5
HIT -6 Scale		69.5	±9.9

Table 5: Comparison of SOD and MDA between Migraine and controls

Parameters	Controls Median (Q3 - Q1)	Migraine Median (Q3- Q1)	p-value
SOD (nm/ml)	41(55-26)	10(12-8)	<0.001*
MDA (U/mL)	2(2-1)	4(5-4)	<0.001*
*p<0.05 was considered statistically significant using Mann Whitney U test			

Figure 1: showing a negative relationship between MDA and SOD, R-square showed 49.2% variation in MDA was explained by SOD for migraine.

DISCUSSIONS

Migraine is one of the most common and disabling neurological disorders worldwide, significantly disrupting patients' quality of life and daily activities. It is primarily a neurovascular disorder with a complex and not fully understood pathophysiology. Epidemiological data from the Western world indicate that approximately 6% of males and 18% of females are affected by migraine. Critical nervous system components implicated in migraine pathogenesis include cranial blood vessels, the trigeminovascular system, and its parasympathetic connections. The pain typically localizes to the frontal and temporal regions but may also radiate to the parietal, occipital, and upper cervical areas (12).

Sex hormones, particularly in females, have been widely recognized as pivotal migraine triggers. Migraine prevalence in women increases following menarche, peaks around age 40, and declines post-menopause. Hormonal fluctuations during menstruation, early pregnancy, and the perimenopausal phase are often associated with increased migraine frequency (13).

In the current study, we also observed a significantly higher prevalence of migraine

among females. This aligns with earlier epidemiological research indicating that women are three times more likely than men to experience migraine (14). Structural and functional MRI findings further support this disparity (15). Moreover, biological and psychosocial factors may contribute to this sex-based difference (16). However, some studies report a higher frequency of migraine episodes in men, particularly those experiencing more than 10 migraine days per month (17).

Currently, migraine diagnosis is based entirely on clinical criteria, as no definitive blood or imaging biomarkers have been established. The condition also has a substantial genetic component, with multiple genes contributing to its development (18).

Our findings revealed a mean age of 33.2 years among migraine patients. This is consistent with prior studies, which report peak onset between the ages of 30 and 39 (19). While the average age appears to be above 30 in several studies, earlier onset has been noted in pediatric populations, with girls aged 14–17 and boys aged 13–15 years

showing increased prevalence in some reports (20).

Obesity has emerged as a global health issue and is recognized as a significant risk factor for numerous chronic conditions. In our study, the mean BMI of migraine patients was 28.4 kg/m² (SD = ±4.8), placing them in the overweight category. A higher BMI (≥25) has been linked to increased risk for chronic headaches (>14 days/month). Other findings support a greater migraine prevalence among individuals undergoing bariatric surgery compared to those with a normal BMI (21). One study reported that obesity is associated with a fivefold increased risk of chronic daily headaches. However, another study did not find any significant differences in migraine characteristics between obese and non-obese women (22).

We recorded a mean systolic blood pressure (SBP) of 121.5 mmHg and a mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) of 81.9 mmHg in migraine patients, values consistent with prior research. However, the relationship between blood pressure and migraine remains controversial due to mixed findings in the literature (23).

Our results also support a familial component in migraine pathophysiology. A stronger family history correlates with earlier onset, increased frequency, and migraine with aura, particularly among males (24).

Sleep disturbances are commonly reported by migraine sufferers, although the precise relationship remains unclear. In our study, 2.4% of patients reported insufficient sleep as a trigger, while 17.1% linked their migraines to insufficient sleep and screen use, and 35% associated attacks with physical activity combined with poor sleep. A further 17.9% identified physical activity, screen time, and insufficient sleep collectively as triggers. High screen time (>6 hours/day) has been reported as a potential migraine risk factor (25). Inadequate hydration also appears to exacerbate migraine severity. Our study aligns with findings that lower water intake is associated with increased migraine disability, frequency, pain intensity, and duration (26). Other research supports this, with hydration found to reduce migraine frequency and intensity (27).

Nausea is a hallmark symptom in migraine classification. Increased migraine intensity has been positively correlated with greater nausea

and other symptoms such as photophobia and phonophobia (28). Our data confirm this, with 78.9% of patients reporting moderate to severe pain. Among symptoms, nausea was reported by 31.7%, nausea/photophobia/phonophobia by 29%, nausea/vomiting by 0.8%, nausea/vomiting/photophobia/phonophobia by 0.8%, phonophobia by 0.8%, photophobia by 24.6%, and photophobia/phonophobia by 0.8%. These results corroborate the synergistic effect described by Drummond, where increased pain and associated symptoms amplify each other, leading to more intense attacks (29).

Superoxide dismutases (SODs) are critical antioxidant metalloenzymes that defend cells against oxidative stress. They counteract reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated during vasoconstriction, vasospasm, and ischemia/reperfusion events. In contrast, malondialdehyde (MDA), a thiobarbituric acid-reactive substance (TBARS), reflects membrane lipid peroxidation due to oxidative stress. In this study, SOD levels were significantly reduced in migraine patients [median: 10 (12–8) nm/ml] compared to healthy controls [41 (55–26) nm/ml], consistent with previous reports (30). However, some studies contradict this finding, showing either unchanged or even elevated SOD activity.

MDA levels were elevated in migraine patients [4 (5–4) U/ml] compared to controls [2 (2–1) U/ml], supporting the role of oxidative damage in migraine pathology. This is in line with previous findings showing increased MDA levels in migraineurs, especially during ictal phases (31). However, some authors have reported no significant differences in MDA levels between migraine patients and controls (32).

Conclusion: Our study provides compelling evidence that migraine patients exhibit significantly reduced levels of superoxide dismutase (SOD), a key antioxidant enzyme, alongside elevated concentrations of malondialdehyde (MDA), a marker of lipid peroxidation. These findings highlight the presence of heightened oxidative stress in individuals with migraines, supporting the hypothesis that oxidative imbalance plays a pivotal role in migraine pathophysiology. The decreased antioxidative defense and increased oxidative damage observed in our study

underscore the need for further research into the mechanisms linking oxidative stress with migraine onset and progression. These insights have the potential to inform the development of more refined and targeted therapeutic strategies aimed at mitigating oxidative damage, thereby improving the quality of life and clinical outcomes for patients suffering from migraines.

ETHICAL APPROVAL:

The ethical approval was taken from the Institutions Review Board of BUHSCK provided IRB and FRC letter prior to the initiation of the research work.

COMPETING INTEREST:

There is no conflict of interest.

PATIENTS' CONSENT:

Informed consents were taken from all patients included in the study, and detailed history was recorded.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION:

AG: Conception and design of work, analysis, collection, compilation and interpretation of data, manuscript writing, review and editing of manuscript and funding of study.

SA: Conception and design of work, analysis and interpretation of data review and editing of manuscript.

OA: Data collection and compilation, review and editing of manuscript.

ST: Data collection, compilation and interpretation and review of manuscript.

SR: Conception and design of work, review and editing of manuscript.

YS: Data collection, compilation and interpretation.

All authors approved the final version of the manuscript to be published.

DISCLAIMER:

This manuscript is a part of my MPhil thesis work.

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